

INNOVATIVE THINKING IN THE WORLDVIEW OF YOUNG PEOPLE

Tursunov Khojimurod Makhammadjan ugli

Andijan Machinery Institute

Direction-Metrology, standardization and
quality management(by industry)

2nd Year Graduate:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7805853>

Annotation: This scientific article pays great attention to the innovative approaches of young people and their ideas, and today a wide range of opportunities is being developed.

Keywords: knowledge, innovation, experience, ability, research, thinking, future.

The innovation potential of young people is an indispensable personality trait that reflects the totality of innovative knowledge, skills and relationships carried out in the process of scientific and practical work, as well as the possibilities and reserve abilities to apply them in educational and future professional activities in the context of innovative economic changes. There are two components in the structure of the innovation potential of young people: clear and hidden. Specific potential is determined by the knowledge and skills of young people in the field of innovation activity, as well as the experience of innovation received during their educational and educational and professional activities. The hidden potential is represented by the development of their innovative thinking. The priority in this process is to encourage young people to acquire innovative knowledge and skills, to enter into innovative activities, to increase the ability to innovate, as well as to raise a number of personal qualities.

The model for the formation of the innovation potential of young people is a pedagogical system aimed at the development of knowledge, skills and experiences in the field of innovation in them, the development of innovative thinking and abilities, as well as personal qualities. In this model, it is important to identify educational goals, select and structure the semantic content of educational and pedagogical interaction of professors and students, create forms, methods and teaching aids, as well as organizational approaches to monitoring and evaluating its results. The integrity of this model is ensured by four components such as goal setting, logical-semantic, active, evaluative and effective activity. The Model is implemented in stages based on such approaches as propedeutic, motivational-modeling, heuristic of the formation of the innovation potential of young people.

Pedagogical conditions for the successful implementation of the model for the formation of the innovation potential of young people include:

- 1) creating an innovative saturated environment in the national education system;
- 2) broadening the directions for the formation of innovative thinking in the educational process through the development of personality-oriented pedagogical technologies that fully respond to the level of intellectual, mental and social development in the educational process;
- 3) design an individual trajectory for each representative of the younger generation to realize the innovation potential, taking into account his intellectual abilities, professional inclinations, extracurricular interests and life experience.

Further raising the national education system based on innovation thinking is one of the pressing issues. Because education is a strategic institution of the state, within the framework of which not only professionalism, but also Civic positivity is formed in young people. If we do not want to face a crisis, but want to preserve our national culture and mentality, then we need to establish the training of professional specialists on a wide scale. Innovations are created precisely by individuals with creative, innovative thinking¹.

Fundamental reforms in the national education system, implemented during the transition to a market economy, and the change in socio-economic conditions for the active functioning of this area associated with them, put new requirements on the composition and content of educational activities of universities. Currently, the economic situation of educational institutions is characterized by the lack of funds necessary for their complete modernization. Innovative processes in education are objective in nature and correspond to the basic nature and forms of human and social development, determining their humanistic nature. These processes ensure the stability of their development and their continuity.

An important aspect of innovation pedagogy is its desire to create a favorable environment for teaching. The dynamics of the development of innovative processes in education depends on socio-political and socio-economic conditions, as well as on subjective factors. These processes are the main source and mechanism of the development of the humanistic tradition in pedagogy, harmonizing personal, social and statewide goals in education: the more favorable conditions are created for the personal, professional development and self-realization of the student, the faster the professional who serves for the benefit of society succeeds.

The social meaning of the educational environment of innovation consists in creating favorable conditions for the training of a specialist, which is a guarantee of the historical perspective of the development of society and the state.

Today, the main directions for the development of the innovation educational environment are: the convergence and convergence of its external and internal components; strengthening the influence of the social factor on the development of the innovation environment; ensuring an increasing dependence on the information and technological component of the dynamics of the development of the innovation environment; developing the research work of the University and; regular accounting of personal, social and national requirements in the composition, organization and content of professional training of university specialists, strengthening the commercialization of innovative ideas (pragmatism); it is important to ensure the priority of educational work carried out with students in the process of professional training.

Innovation changes the entire system of human relations with the outside world and with itself. Innovation is, first of all, the openness of ideas and views of different natures that differ from their point of view. The novelty is to look openly into the past, today and the future. The paradox of such a novelty is that it effectively solves modern problems only on the basis of a traditional and innovative approach. Innovation, when looking into the future, relies in many ways on the ideas of the past. The main features of the innovative approach will be: "pre-conscious enjoyment", "collaboration" and "co-creation".

¹ Tsvetkova V.D. Innovation and innovation in the culture of personal self-realization: dissertation ... candidate of Philosophical Sciences. - Chelyabinsk, 2009. - 162 p.

The presence of mechanisms of self - preservation and self-development in the concept of innovation is explained by the fact that it meets the criterion of dialectics-a system that meets the Basic Laws of dialectics, works and develops in accordance with these laws, forming the basis of its internal consistency. However, this does not mean at all that innovative concepts of the past can be repeated in the previous form. The objectively developing direction of historical progress and its conditions sometimes presuppose the possibility of applying the ideas of the past. The emergence of innovations is associated with the establishment of new paradigms and attitudes towards the goals and principles of the national education system of young people, the formation of a new system of social values that opens up historical prospects for each individual and society as a whole².

Innovational activity is a process that develops in thinking through the content of new knowledge and understanding of the generation of innovations. On this basis, we can create a model of the mechanism of innovative thinking as a process (an effort to create innovation in the form of a qualitatively new product of thinking), which leads to the emergence of innovation on the basis of subjective consciousness for the objective, Real world. This process is based on the study of the mental model, which is associated with a consistent, holistic analysis of a problem situation, which uniquely shapes the perception of the world, is an analogy inherent in the processing and storage of information and the self-determination of the individual in it. The epistemological aspect of the mental model is as follows: the mental model is the reflection in thought of the world or part of it that surrounds us. This is reflected in knowledge about the object in the form of information and energy exchange. The formation of the mental model is achieved by transferring a certain energy of the subject of knowledge to various forms of information in the process of its construction. A mental model is a subjective reality of an individual based on some type of integrity or part of an objective reality. In the process of reflection of mental models as subjective realities, new ideas, structures, schemes, models can be formed that differ from analogs that occur in the objective world.

Innovative thinking creates mental models that are still unknown to humanity. This process creates a completely new subjective reality, which is determined by the possibility of their production and recognition in practice.

The emergence of innovative mental models depends on a number of factors::

- dissatisfaction with traditional approaches, the need to update outdated paradigms, the desire to radically change goals in education;
- the need to apply non-standard approaches to the formation of an educational and educational system that reveals to young people the main meanings of personal, social, professional and national life;
- the need to constantly improve the level of professionalism and competence of young people;
- the presence of the possibility of systematic and continuous information access by the subject in the process of developing the problem under study;
- these include those whose motivation for Education, Initiative and creativity is new, that is, the search for, development of something that has not existed before, etc.

² Zhabina V.V. Risks of innovative development of society: socio-philosophical analysis: dissertation... Candidate of Philosophical Sciences: - Saratov, 2013. - 167 p.

Innovation, as a rule, occurs in the form of an unconventional idea - the image of future changes, which is then carried out in theoretical stages. Creativity can also have a reconstructive character that does not affect the basic principles of the system. However, such creativity "passes" towards innovation. Innovation thinking is the search for objective reality (including in a collective way) by the subject, exalting his personal and social position.

The formation of innovation potential is achieved through the intellectual, psychological and socially oriented activities of young people through the development of innovative knowledge, skills and skills necessary for the implementation of educational and future professional activities. The mechanism for the formation of innovation potential is the desire of young people to continue their future professional activities in the context of innovative changes and the formation of a sufficient level of knowledge, skills and abilities to independently solve the problems of innovation that arise in scientific and practical activities.

"Innovation is a multifaceted, socio-economic process in essence. This process is of constant dynamic nature and never stops. Continuity is its most important feature. Meanwhile, this process does not exclude the fact that a certain period interval is relatively separated and also treated as a social Real reality. Innovation is not a process that will be chegeralized within a separate country, region. Scientific and technical thinking can be viewed as the initial stage of innovation. Only a person with scientific thinking and skills will be able to create a new technology"³. Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁴ When it comes to corruption in education, a thousand unfortunately continue to increase as much as it is fought against it.

The modern world is characterized by the emergence of economic systems, in which competitive advantages are provided not by resources and cheap labor, but by knowledge, information and innovation. Such economic systems form the basis of an innovational society. The concept of innovation covers the creation and dissemination of news, as well as related changes in the way of activity and thinking. Innovation thinking is understood as a new way of thinking within the framework of scientific and technical progress and innovative processes in society, including education. The need for a person's ability to adapt in a modern innovation society is associated with the process of moving education to pedagogical innovations aimed at developing reproductive thinking (a knowledge-based approach), creating and developing innovation, effective, creative thinking (a competency-based approach).

³ Khadzhiev U.Sh.the role of Oriental spiritual and moral imperatives in the formation of Youth thinking. Author of a doctor of Philosophy (PhD) dissertation in philosophical Sciences. - Tashkent 2020. –P.18.

⁴ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). Eastern Renaissance And Its Cultural Heritage: The View Of Foreign Researchers. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

References:

1. Tsvetkova V.D. Innovation and innovation in the culture of personal self-realization: dissertation ... candidate of Philosophical Sciences. - Chelyabinsk, 2009. - 162 p.
2. Zhabina V.V. Risks of innovative development of society: socio-philosophical analysis: dissertation... Candidate of Philosophical Sciences: - Saratov, 2013. - 167 p.
3. Khadzhiev U.Sh. the role of Oriental spiritual and moral imperatives in the formation of Youth thinking. Author of a doctor of Philosophy (PhD) dissertation in philosophical Sciences. - Tashkent 2020. - P.18.
4. Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). Eastern Renaissance And Its Cultural Heritage: The View Of Foreign Researchers. ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions, 2(05), 211-215.